

The Struggle of Suffering in Antiquity

On January 5, 1955, The Christian Century magazine released an article on ancient predecessors to the biblical book of Job lauding the work of Samuel N. Kramer, the Clark Research Professor of Assyriology at the University of Pennsylvania. It said, “Thus from the literature of the earliest known civilization, which inspired many familiar stories in the Old Testament, has come another ‘first.’”¹

According to this viewpoint, the biblical Book of Job was no more unique than it was first. It was a work “inspired,” not by God but by “the literature of earliest known civilizations.” At least one fact from the article is true. Many works in antiquity were written with themes like what one finds in Job. Kenton Sparks lists several such works with a brief description.

Dialogue Between a Man and His God – An Akkadian work dating to the Old Babylonian period where a suffering man speaks with his god. His god tells him never to forget him.

Ludlul Bel Nemeqi – Another Akkadian work from the Kassite period. Subsi-Mesre-Sakkan lost his position, wealth, family, and health and appealed to the gods.

The Babylonian Theodicy – a sufferer is accused of arrogance and blasphemy and is abandoned by his friends. He proclaims his innocence while acknowledging the gulf between human and divine wisdom.

The Dialogue of Pessimism – a master and his slave, in an interplay of serious conversation and sarcasm, dialog about the problem of evil and how to respond to it. They conclude that life is vanity.²

¹ Anonymous, “Discover Sumerian Job: Scholars at University of Pennsylvania Unearth Prototype of Biblical Hero,” *Christian Century Magazine*, Chicago, IL, January 5, 1955, 30.

² Kenton L. Sparks, *Ancient Texts for the Study of the Hebrew Bible: A Guide to the Background Literature*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2005, 61-64.

What should one make of such works? Do they prove Job to be only another iteration of a common question asked in antiquity (as well as in modernity), “Why do bad things happen to good people?” Joshua J. Mark says,

There is no question that a number of biblical narratives of the Old Testament have their origins in Sumerian works. The Fall of Man and Noah's Flood in Genesis, for example, can be traced back to the Sumerian works. There exists today the claim that *The Book of Job* was derived from the earlier work in the same way as the Flood story. While there is, obviously, some merit to this claim and a comparison is profitable, it seems a disservice to both works to only read them for what they offer regarding literary borrowing.³

Mark’s “disservice” is not that people say *Job* is just another iteration of an age-old question, but that they do not read each work for what it offers. The “disservice” is when one sees only literary borrowing and misses the wisdom contained in each.

B. Lynne Newell added this insight, “The findings of archaeology have demonstrated that economic and cultural exchange took place. In the field of literature, a fragment of the Mesopotamian Gilgamesh Epic from about the thirteenth century B.C. has been found at Megiddo in Palestine. Mesopotamian wisdom texts have also been found at Ugarit.”⁴ Thus, there was an exchange of ideas and literature across cultures, and one could easily conclude that someone in the world of Judaism was copying this idea and presenting it with a Jewish twist, sort of like ancient plagiarism. But while the writer of Job may have known of these works this does not prove or disprove Job’s uniqueness.

In a letter that this student wrote to a skeptical family member, this was the primary issue of debate.

At first glance, you, and others like you who hold to “spirituality” and “it’s all the same story and same god” viewpoint, would find your perspective confirmed. *The Book of Job* is not the only one of its kind. Several ancient texts have been unearthed which tell the stories

³ Joshua J. Mark, “The Ludlul-Bel-Nimeqi - Not Merely a Babylonian Job,” <https://www.ancient.eu/article/226/the-ludlul-bel-nimeqi---not-merely-a-babylonian-job/>, March 6, 2011.

⁴ B. Lynne Newell, “Job: Repentant or Rebellious,” *Westminster Theological Journal*, 46 (1984), 298-316, 300.

of innocent people who suffered. . . . The treatise closest to Job is called “Ludlu bel Nemeqi” which translates to, “I will praise the lord of wisdom” and which describes a pious but not necessarily innocent person who suffers from an illness. He is rejected by his peers, his brother becomes an enemy, and the gods ignore him. At this point, some writers (probably some you have read) have seen this and said, “Yep. Just as I thought. The Bible is not unique.” Depending on their perspective, they might conclude, “It’s all the same nonsense,” or “It’s all the same wonderful story.” But this would be a grave error.⁵

It would be a grave error! John Walton has enumerated differences between the biblical story and Ancient Near Eastern stories. These are not slight variations. For example, the *Sumerian Job* is retrospective with a praise-lament-restoration-praise structure while *The Dialog of Pessimism* is a conversation between a master and his slave, and it is closer to *Ecclesiastes* than to *Job*. These are minor variations. Job differs at the worldview level in seven ways.

First, in Ancient Near Eastern Thinking (ANET), calamity occurs when one offends the gods for not carrying out the religious rituals properly. This, despite the gods not revealing how these should take place! Thus, if one got the right combination in ritual one could expect blessing. If not, curses would come.⁶

Sarah J. Denning-Bolle underscores this point in her essay on ancient wisdom. She points out that the label, “Wisdom Literature,” is a modern label imposed on antiquity. In our modern “wisdom,” we distinguish between practical, day-to-day wisdom and highly speculative metaphysical wisdom which seeks to grasp the nature of things. But in antiquity, this was a false dichotomy. Wisdom refers to “skill in cult and magic lore, and the wise man is the initiate”⁷ in these practices. Modern people would call this superstition and foolishness. Thus, the theodicies

⁵ Correspondence between Jonathan Williams and Michael Fortino, June 23, 2019.

⁶ John H. Walton, *NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, “How the Book of Job Differs from Ancient Near Eastern Thinking,” Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2016, 824-826, 824.

⁷ Sara J. Denning-Bolle, “Wisdom and Dialogue in The Ancient Near East,” *Numen*, Vol. XXXIV, Fase. 2.

of ANET often present the wise solution to suffering as getting the rituals right. In contrast, Job proclaims his innocence. He has not failed God in any way. His steadfast insistence on his righteousness undercuts ANET.

Second, ANET emphasized The Great Symbiosis. Humans were made to take care of the gods by growing food for their consumption, and the gods would, in turn, take care of them.⁸ There was no orthodoxy, only orthopraxy. The gods did not require moral behavior except when it threatened the social order. Thus, one could, theoretically, perform proper rituals during the day and sleep with a prostitute at night. The gods were not considered ontologically righteous and were capricious. They slept around too!

Third, the structure of Job undercuts the Great Symbiosis. Satan's accusation is, "Job does not serve you for nothing! He carries out his rituals and you bless. He is no different from anyone else!" Walton explains:

If Job's response to his suffering indicates that he is bound to this matrix, the adversary has won his case. In other words, if Job is not different from all the sufferers in the Mesopotamian world shown in its literature, the adversary has made his point. All of the Mesopotamian texts end by affirming the traditional dogmas. In Job, those same traditional dogmas are voiced by his friends, and they are persistently rejected by Job. Thus, the premise of the entire work undercuts ANET.⁹

Fourth, the sufferers in various theodicies are ready to acknowledge their guilt for failing to carry out the rituals properly. But Job consistently maintains his innocence, and his words would have been shocking to ancient ears.

And Job continued his discourse: "As surely as God lives, who has denied me justice, the Almighty, who has made my life bitter, as long as I have life within me, the breath of God in my nostrils, my lips will not say anything wicked, and my tongue will not utter lies. I will never admit you are in the right; till I die, I will not deny my integrity. I will maintain my innocence and never let go of it; my conscience will not reproach me as long as I live. (Job 27:1-6)

⁸ Walton, 825.

⁹ Ibid., 825.

Fifth, demons, acting independently from the gods, bring suffering to the people in ANET. In the *Ludlul Bel Nemeqi*, the sufferer stays faithful to Marduk and encourages others to be faithful. Marduk sends an exorcist to expel the demon who oppressed him.¹⁰ Demons afflict humans because the gods turn their backs on people who have offended them. This is absent from Job. Yes, an adversary is involved, but God is present from beginning to end, and the affliction is not from God angrily turning from Job for his failures.

Sixth, theodicies in ANET always ended in praise to the gods. Job does not end in praise which was unique in the ancient world. The Great Symbiosis was not in play. Instead, a covenant relationship between YHWH and his people was in force. A relationship, not rigid performance of ritual, was the binding factor between God and his people.

Finally, in the ANET texts, sufferers are never innocent. In Job, he is innocent from beginning to end. God tells him to pray for his friends! Walton concludes, “It is evident that the philosophical and theological answers provided by the book of Job are quite different from those offered in the ancient Near Eastern exemplars. Job rejects the easy answers of Mesopotamia.”¹¹

Thus, while there are similarities between Job and the theodicies of the ANE, similarity is not sameness. Yes, Job was written in the cognitive environment of its time. There is no other way it could have been done. But it was written to undercut the pervasive worldview of its time. One finds similarities and can welcome and learn from ancient sources that illumine our understanding of ancient thinking and Scripture. Digging deeper, however, one finds that the Bible presents a different story, a different worldview, a different God, and a different way of knowing him – through a covenant relationship, not ritual.

¹⁰ Sparks, 62.

¹¹ Walton, 826.

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